

Comparison of Discrete and Continuous Variable Quantum Key Distribution in Passive Optical Networks

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Abstract Integrating quantum key distribution (QKD) into passive optical networks (PONs) poses challenges due to high losses from passive splitters and spontaneous Raman scattering noise from coexisting classical channels. This paper compares the performance of upstream discrete-variable and continuous-variable QKD systems in single-fibre bidirectional PONs. ©2024 The Author(s)

Introduction

Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) assures information-theoretic secure exchange of cryptographic keys based on the fundamental laws of quantum physics. Since 1984, several QKD protocols have been proposed and can be mainly divided into two categories: discrete-variable (DV)^[1] and continuous-variable (CV)^[2] QKD. In the former, the quantum information carriers are single-photon signals, which are mostly implemented by using faint laser pulses; in the latter the information is encoded on the quadratures of light, typically using off-the-shelf IQ modulators. At the receiver (Bob) side, DV-QKD requires single-photon detectors, whose footprint and cost can still be improved, whereas CV-QKD is compatible with coherent receivers developed for telecommunication applications. The adoption of QKD services depends on the successful integration of QKD systems into the communication legacy infrastructures while coexisting with high-power classical channels, sources of the spontaneous Raman scattering (SpRS) crosstalk^[3].

Most of the analyses presented in the literature evaluate QKD performance in point-to-point links in coexistence with dense wavelength division multiplexed (DWDM) communication channels. CV-QKD can better tolerate linear and nonlinear crosstalk induced by classical channels thanks to the inherent filtering property of coherent detection^[4]; moreover, the secret key rate (SKR) achievable by CV-QKD systems is higher than DV-QKD one for limited loss links^[5]. On the other hand, DV-QKD reaches longer distances and supports higher losses^[5]. However, the endpoints of secure communication services belong to the access network segment^[6], mainly provided by passive optical networks (PONs). PONs use passive optical splitters to support point-to-multipoint connections between a single

optical line terminal (OLT) and multiple optical network units (ONUs). The access network is, therefore, a very challenging scenario for the provision of a QKD network layer, due to the high optical distribution network (ODN) losses and the coexistence with classical channels, generating SpRS noise over the entire spectrum^[7]. As DV- and CV-QKD technologies present opposite resilience levels concerning these two issues, it would be interesting to compare their performance in the access network scenario.

In recent years, several studies have been conducted on the integration of either DV^{[8]–[11]} or CV^{[12]–[14]} QKD systems in PONs. However, a comprehensive comparison of the two technologies to bolster a quantum-secured layer in coexistence with an extensive set of PON standards is still missing. In this paper, we analyse the performance of upstream DV- and CV-QKD systems in terms of supported secret key rate (SKR), when integrated in a single-fibre bidirectional PON (Fig. 1) in the presence of GPON^[15], XG-PON^[16], NG-PON2^[17] or HS-PON^[18] classical channels.

Theoretical model

Most of the proposals for the integration of DV-QKD systems in PONs rely on the deployment of the quantum receiver at the OLT side, while the quantum transmitter (Alice) is located at the ONU side (Fig. 1). The upstream (US) quantum access network allows the sharing of single-photon detectors' cost and complexity among multiple

Fig. 1: Upstream quantum access network in single-fibre bidirectional PON

users, which are managed by the time-division multiple access (TDMA), as for the US classical transmission. The SKR performance will thus depend on the actual number of users requesting a secure communication service. Although CV-QKD systems can operate using a downstream (DS) CV-QKD access network protocol, obtaining the simultaneous key distribution between one Alice and multiple Bobs^[19], in the following analysis we will compare both QKD technologies considering the same upstream quantum access network. The SKR, obtained in the asymptotic limit of infinite-key, will be expressed in terms of bit/channel usage (either symbols or pulses) for both the considered categories, and thus the final SKR will be proportional to the repetition rate allowed to each user by the TDMA.

For the security analyses, we consider a Gaussian modulation CV-QKD under the collective attack in a trusted heterodyne receiver scenario^[20] and the decoy-state BB84 protocol for DV-QKD^[21]. The SKRs are, respectively, given by:

$$R_{CV} \approx \beta I_{AB} - \chi_{BE} \quad (1)$$

$$R_{DV} \approx Q_1[1 - H(e_1)] - f_e Q_\mu H(E_\mu) \quad (2)$$

where β is the reconciliation efficiency, I_{AB} is the mutual information between Alice and Bob, χ_{BE} is the Holevo information; Q_1 is the gain of single-photon pulses, e_1 is their error rate, Q_μ is the overall gain, E_μ is the overall QBER, f_e is the error correction efficiency and $H(x)$ is the binary Shannon entropy. See^{[20],[21]} for detailed discussion and derivation. In both security analyses, a critical role is played by the transmittance T and the noise, which is defined as excess noise ξ_{Bob} in CV systems and as background count rate Y_0 in the DV analysis. The transmittance of the quantum channel in a PON infrastructure is given by:

$$T = S_1 S_2 e^{-\alpha_q L} \quad (3)$$

where S_i are the splitting ratios of the ODN passive splitters, α_q is the attenuation coefficient of the quantum channel and L is the total PON length. The noise contribution reaching the quantum receiver includes the in-band SpRS generated by DS and US classical channels. The SpRS spectral density N_R at Bob input, which is affected by the splitting ratios and the position of the splitters, can be evaluated by the theoretical model we developed in^[7] to address the specific features of the point-to-multipoint PON ODN. Based on^{[22],[23]}, we can estimate the excess noise and the background count rate as:

$$\xi_{Bob} = \xi_{bg} + 2 \frac{\lambda_q^3}{hc^2} N_R \eta_{CV} \quad (4)$$

$$Y_0 = 2p_d + \frac{\lambda_q^3}{hc^2} N_R \Delta\nu \Delta t \eta_{DV} \quad (5)$$

Tab. 1: Classical and quantum channel specifications: wavelength in [nm], power in [dBm]

	λ_{DS}	P_C^{DS}	λ_{US}	P_C^{US}	λ_q
GPON	1480	5.5	1290	5.2	1280
XG-PON	1575	4.5	1280	5.2	1420
NG-PON2	1596	5.5	1524	7.2	1310
HS-PON	1344	9.0	1310	7.2	1675

where ξ_{bg} is the background excess noise experienced by Bob without coexisting classical channels, λ_q is the wavelength of the quantum channel, h is the Planck constant, c is the speed of light, p_d is the proper dark counts of the single-photon detector, $\Delta\nu$ is the bandwidth of the band-pass filter used at Bob side, Δt is the gate interval of Bob's detector and $\eta_{CV(DV)}$ is the transmittance of the CV(DV)-QKD receiver, including internal losses and quantum efficiency of the detector.

Results

We developed a simulation tool that provides the SKR of CV and DV QKD systems in PON infrastructures with a different number of users N (i.e., $N = (S_1 S_2)^{-1}$) as a function of the total fibre length. The considered network architecture is shown in Fig.1 with fixed trunk $L_t=2$ km and distribution $L_d=0.5$ km fibre lengths, and variable feeder fibre L_f length between 2.5 and 17.5 km. Classical channels match the specifications of the standard physical media dependent layer for N1 PON classes and are indicated in Tab. 1; the table reports also the considered QKD wavelengths belonging to the optimal quantum-available bandwidths obtained in^[7]. The simulation parameters are representative of typical CV- and DV- QKD systems and are reported in Tab. 2: V_A is the modulation variance, V_{el} is the trusted electronic noise, μ is the signal state expected photon number and e_{mis} is the misalignment error probability. Fig. 2 shows the SKRs in coexistence with GPON classical channels, which are placed in C- and O-

Fig. 2: GPON: SKR vs PON length for different N ; CV-QKD (solid line), DV-QKD (dashed line).

Tab. 2: QKD system parameters (CV on the left, DV on the right):
 V_A in [SNU], V_{el} and ξ_{bg} in [mSNU], $\Delta\nu$ in [GHz], Δt in [ns]

V_A	V_{el}	β	ξ_{bg}	η_{CV}	μ	e_{mis}	f_e	$\Delta\nu$	Δt	η_{DV}	p_d
8	63	0.95	0.2	0.44	0.6	3.2e-3	1.15	12.5	1	0.16	1e-5

bands, generating SpRS over the entire spectrum. The chosen quantum wavelength λ_q belongs to the lower O-band, where low anti-Stokes SpRS noise is generated. Up to 4 users, the CV system outperforms the DV one over the entire PON length due to low splitter losses. With 8 and 16 users, secure keys can not be distributed with CV-QKD beyond 17 km and the CV-SKR is higher than DV-one only for short links. On the other hand, DV systems support up to 64 users in more than 13 km-long access networks. As reported in^[7], XG-PON is the most critical standard for integrating a DV-QKD layer due to the presence of Stokes and Anti-Stokes SpRS contributions. CV systems, having a higher resilience to crosstalk, ensure better SKR performance and longer reaches (Fig. 3). However, when ODN losses increase, i.e. with 32 or 64 users, only DV-QKD is supported even though for less than 7-km links. The spectral allocation of DS and US classical channels in NG-PON2 and HS-PON simplifies the quantum wavelength assignment. The coexistence with NG-PON2 (Fig. 4) assures the highest SKRs for both CV- and DV-QKD, owing to low anti-Stokes SpRS noise and low O-band losses. Similarly to the GPON scenario, the CV-QKD technology performs better than DV-QKD up to 16 km in an 8-user PON and up to 10 km with 16 users, but only DV-QKD can be supported in PONs hosting 32 or 64 users. In the case of HS-PON coexistence (Fig. 5), due to the generation of the SpRS in the more efficient Stokes regime, the performance of the CV-QKD system are less affected than the DV-QKD ones, thanks to crosstalk noise resilience; however, when splitting losses increase, it is the DV-QKD resilience towards channel transmittance that guarantees a higher SKR.

Fig. 3: XG-PON: SKR vs PON length for different N; CV-QKD (solid line), DV-QKD (dashed line).

Fig. 4: NG-PON2: SKR vs PON length for different N; CV-QKD (solid line), DV-QKD (dashed line).

Fig. 5: HS-PON: SKR vs PON length for different N; CV-QKD (solid line), DV-QKD (dashed line).

Conclusions

This work analyses the integration of QKD systems in PONs, by comparing the performance of upstream CV- and DV- systems in coexistence with standard-compliant classical channels. In the most challenging scenarios in terms of SpRS noise generation, such as the integration with XG-PON standard, CV-QKD shows its better resilience to crosstalk. Moreover, for all PON standards in networks with up to 8 users, CV-QKD provides higher SKRs. This technology can also rely on the mature classical coherent transceiver technologies, better matching access network requests in terms of footprint and costs. However, only DV-QKD systems are able to distribute quantum secure keys in ODNs serving up to 64 users, thus complying with PON standards. The analysis of downstream CV-QKD protocols^[19] and the experimental evaluation will be considered in future works.

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